

Social and ethnic-racial inequities of physical accessibility to farmers' markets in Porto Alegre, Brazil

Desigualdades sociais e étnico-raciais na acessibilidade física aos mercados de produtores rurais em Porto Alegre, Brasil

Desigualdades sociales y étnico-raciales en la accesibilidad física a los mercados de agricultores en Porto Alegre, Brasil

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Resumo As feiras livres são espaços importantes para a venda de frutas, verduras e legumes, considerados um dos aspectos-chave para cidades saudáveis. Este estudo adota uma abordagem ecológica com ênfase geográfico-espacial para descrever a acessibilidade às feiras livres em Porto Alegre-RS, por quatro modos de transporte (a pé, bicicleta, ônibus e carro) e sua associação com a renda e a raça/cor de pele dos indivíduos. A distribuição das feiras pela cidade é mais equilibrada do que outros estabelecimentos de alimentos, embora a acessibilidade física seja desigual entre os diferentes modos de transporte: a capacidade de alcançar uma feira a pé em 10 minutos ou menos é restrita a menos de 25% da população, enquanto quase 90% podem fazê-lo dirigindo um carro. Encontrou-se uma associação direta e positiva entre os níveis de acessibilidade às feiras e a renda: as localidades mais ricas podem chegar às feiras em menos tempo usando qualquer modo de transporte do que as mais pobres ($p < 0,001$). Regiões com maioria de habitantes brancos têm acessibilidade significativamente melhor às feiras a pé, de bicicleta e de ônibus ($p < 0,01$).

Palavras-chave Iniquidades, Acessibilidade urbana, Raça/cor de pele, Alimentos saudáveis, Feiras livres

Abstract Farmers' markets are important spaces for the commercialization of fruits and vegetables, which access by the urban population is considered one of the key aspects of healthy cities. This study adopts an ecological approach with geographic-spatial emphasis to describe accessibility to farmers' markets in Porto Alegre-RS, by four different modes of transport (walking, bicycle, bus, and car) and their associations with income and race/skin color. The distribution of markets across the city is more balanced than other food establishments, although physical accessibility is highly uneven across modes of transport: the ability to reach a market on foot in 10 minutes or less is restricted to no more than 25% of the population, while almost 90% can do it by driving a car. The study found a direct and positive association between levels of accessibility to farmers' markets and income: wealthier areas can reach fairs in less time using any mode of transport than poorer ones ($p < 0.001$). Regions with a majority of white inhabitants have better accessibility to the fairs on foot, by bicycle, and by bus ($p < 0.01$) than regions with a majority of Black, Indigenous, or yellow populations

Key words Social inequities, Urban accessibility, Race/skin color, Nutrition, Farmers' market.

Resumen Los mercados al aire libre son espacios importantes para la venta de frutas y verduras, considerado uno de los aspectos clave para las ciudades saludables. Este estudio adopta un enfoque ecológico con énfasis geográfico-espacial para describir la accesibilidad a los mercados al aire libre en Porto Alegre-RS, por cuatro modos de transporte (caminar, bicicleta, autobús y automóvil) y su asociación con el ingreso y la etnicidad/color de piel de los individuos. La distribución de los mercados al aire libre en la ciudad es más equilibrada que la de otros establecimientos de comida, aunque la accesibilidad física es desigual entre los diferentes modos de transporte: la capacidad de llegar a un mercado al aire libre a pie en 10 minutos o menos está restringida a menos del 25% de la población, mientras que casi el 90% puede hacerlo conduciendo un coche. Se encontró una asociación directa y positiva entre los niveles de accesibilidad a los mercados al aire libre y los ingresos: las localidades más ricas pueden llegar estos mercados en menos tiempo utilizando cualquier medio de transporte que las más pobres ($p < 0,001$). Las regiones con una mayoría de habitantes blancos tienen una accesibilidad significativamente mejor a los mercados a pie, en bicicleta y en autobús ($p < 0,01$).

Palabras clave Inequidades, Accesibilidad urbana, Etnicidad/color de piel, Alimentos saludables, Mercados al aire libre

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Introduction

The promotion of shorter food sales circuits is considered a crucial global agenda, as shortening food chains can contribute to multiple objectives outlined in the United Nations Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development. Specifically, this aids in advancing Responsible Consumption and Production (Sustainable Development Goal 12)¹. Farmers' markets play a pivotal role in these shorter marketing circuits for food by establishing direct relationships between producers and consumers, thereby ensuring the economic and social sustainability of small-scale farmers. They integrate food and nutritional security systems in numerous Brazilian cities and regions, representing a sustainable strategy for urban food supply².

Traditionally, the Brazilian population buys fresh or minimally processed foods, such as fruits and vegetables (FV), in farmers' markets³. A study carried out in Porto Alegre found that farmers' markets are one of the main places to buy food among people who have a healthy eating pattern, mainly composed of FV⁴. This suggests that these markets serve as indicators of healthier food environments, as their presence nearby can encourage the purchase of foods with higher nutritional value, often at lower prices compared to other traditional food establishments⁵.

Physically, farmers' markets are temporary retail spaces occupying streets and public areas on specific days and times⁶, their locations are defined by food supply decentralization policies to ensure accessibility for the entire city's population⁷. However, previous studies in Brazil have found that farmers' markets are predominantly situated in central city regions and near higher-income populations⁸⁻¹⁰. This tendency may contribute to lower FV consumption among socially disadvantaged populations. Several social determinants, including income, education, race/skin color¹¹, along with environmental factors like the availability of establishments selling these products and urban spatial accessibility, influence FV consumption. Hence, the barriers faced by individuals from lower social positions in accessing farmers' markets can perpetuate a pattern of social health inequalities in Brazilian cities.

Most of the studies that studied farmers' market accessibility in Brazil adopt container approaches to measure spatial accessibility, assessing the co-location of individuals and establishments, that is, the belonging of both to the

same geographic area (neighborhoods, census tracts or buffers around the dwellings). An alternative, more realistic approach that has become the standard is the use of accessibility indicators that effectively calculate the possibility of people physically reaching certain destinations (whether they are places of supply, employment, study, or leisure), located in any part of the city, using any actual mode of transport (walking, bicycle, bus and car) and moving through the streets of the city's street network¹². The study aims to describe the level of physical accessibility to farmers' markets in Porto Alegre and its associations with income and race/skin color of inhabitants.

Methods

Study design and population

This study employs an ecological approach with a focus on spatial analysis, conducted using secondary data from Porto Alegre-RS, Brazil. In Porto Alegre, the municipal government has overseen the organization of farmers' markets since the 1950s, with the enactment of Municipal Decree No. 474 that regulated their operation and assigned specific locations for the markets. These locations were determined based on criteria such as neighborhood demographic density and proximity to wholesale centers. Subsequent legislations have been implemented over the years to regulate various aspects of these markets, as well as other forms of street commerce. However, these measures have not significantly altered their quantity or locations¹³.

Unit of analysis

Based on data from the 2010 Brazilian Census, the Access to Opportunities project, spearheaded by IPEA (*Instituto de Pesquisa Econômica Avançada*), reconfigured the information initially gathered and consolidated in census tracts. This was achieved by aggregating the data into a spatial grid composed of hexagonal cells with a 357-meter diagonal. This grid system is known as "H3 - Hexagonal hierarchical geospatial indexing system", developed and made accessible by the Uber company (<https://h3geo.org/>).

This homogeneous zoning and grouping system eliminates the issue known as the "Modifiable Areal Unit Problem" (MAUP), which arises when using spatial units that lack uniformity in shape and size and exhibit considerable

variability in physical elements, as is the case with Brazilian census tracts¹⁴. Particularly for an analysis primarily focused on measuring actual distances and travel times, such heterogeneity can introduce biases in calculations. Hence, adopting an MAUP-free system, such as the hexagonal grid, is justified. In Porto Alegre, the grid consists of 6,114 hexagonal cells, of which, for this study, only those with at least one inhabitant in 2010 were taken into account, resulting in a sample of 3,232 cells (52.8%).

Sociodemographic data

The data processed by IPEA provided information on the total population, the count and proportion of white, black, brown, indigenous, or yellow residents, as well as the average per capita household income. Race/skin color and income variables were transformed into binary categories. In the first instance, every cell with over 25.5% of the population (representing the $\geq 3^{\text{rd}}$ quartile of the 2010 distribution) made up of ethnic-racial minorities (black, brown, indigenous, and yellow) was categorized as “high presence” of these population groups, while the rest were classified as “low presence”. In the second case, every hexagon with an average income value below BRL 474.35 (representing the $\leq 1^{\text{st}}$ quartile) was labeled as “lower income”, while the remaining cells were designated as “higher income”.

Data on food markets

Data regarding the type, location, days, and operating hours of the markets were gathered from the Porto Alegre City Hall webpage in August 2022 in the form of a geospatial file. This file contains addresses and geographic coordinates, enabling precise location within the city space. Each market's location was correlated with the grid, facilitating the creation of an origins-and-destinations matrix (with cells containing population as origins and cells housing markets as destinations).

The three types of farmers' markets existing in the city – (I) conventional farmers' markets, recognized as “model markets” [*“feiras modelo”*]; (II) farmers' markets; and (III) ecological farmers' markets, exclusively vending organic and agroecological foods – were consolidated into a single category. This consolidation was made considering that they all predominantly sell fresh foods, especially fruits and vegetables (FV).

Additionally, the location data for other types of food establishments in Porto Alegre for 2020 were examined for comparative analysis. These data, obtained from the State Treasury Department of Rio Grande do Sul, were categorized according to the nature of the products sold, following the criteria outlined in the 2018 Technical Mapping of Food Deserts prepared by CAISAN (Interministerial Chamber for Food and Nutrition Security). The categories included: i) exclusively or primarily unprocessed or minimally processed foods; ii) mixed products, typically incorporating on-site food services (such as bakeries and restaurants); iii) exclusively or primarily ultra-processed foods (e.g., confectionery, snack bars, fast-food outlets); and iv) grocery stores and supermarkets, evaluated separately based on the variety of products offered.

Analyses

The analysis of the distribution of food retail and farmers' markets in geographic space started with the NNI (Nearest Neighborhood Index) which computes the average distances between each point and the nearest point and divides this number by the expected average distance in a hypothetical random distribution with the same number of points covering the same area. The closer this value is to 0, the more concentrated the distribution is¹⁵.

To assess the physical accessibility of the population to markets (destination), the Minimum Travel Time (MTT) indicator was used. This is the minimum travel time (in minutes) from each cell with population (origin) by each mode of transport to the closest cell with markets available¹⁶.

The IPEA script package *r5r*, designed for the R software, was utilized to compute the route between each origin-destination pair. This calculation considered Porto Alegre's actual road network and incorporated four distinct modes of transportation: walking, cycling, public transport (bus), and car. In the case of walking and cycling, the algorithm seeks the shortest path between the origin and the destination along any accessible road. However, for the car, it factors in driving routes, traffic lights, and any other limitations present in the city of Porto Alegre's spatial road network model (<https://dadosabertos.poa.br/>).

For bus trips, the code uses the same network as automobiles but adds the itineraries of the lines, the location of the bus stops and the frequency of the vehicles, available in the GTFS

(General Transit Feed Specification) (<https://gtfs.org/>) – from Porto Alegre, in 2019, (POA Dados Abertos: <https://dadosabertos.poa.br/>). The calculation considers the path (generally traveled on foot) between the centroid of the cell of origin and the nearest bus stop, the route of the bus line between this and the bus stop closest to the market(s), as well as the final path (on foot) between both. Consequently, the total travel time by bus is the combined duration of walking times, waiting times, and the actual bus journey itself.

The code specifications have incorporated off-peak hours to calculate travel times by car and bus. This decision is based on the observation that motorized trips for purchasing food at farmers' markets typically occur between 9:00 am and 12:00 pm, as well as between 2:00 pm and 6:00 pm, deliberately avoiding the periods of 7-9:00 am, 12-1:00 pm, and 6-8:00 pm. These timeframes were considered non-peak hours for travel estimation¹⁷.

From the iteration of the search for routes and the calculation of the respective travel times between each point of origin and each of the markets for each of the travel modes, we classified the resulting times into 4 intervals: up to 10 minutes, 10 to 20 minutes, 20 to 30 minutes, and over 30 minutes.

Differences in accessibility between modes of transport and between cells with higher and lower income and with higher and lower presence of ethnic-racial minority residents were described by absolute and relative frequency, and their association was tested through Pearson's chi-square for heterogeneity and linear trend, adopting a significance level of 5%. The data were treated statistically in the R software 4.2.1 and GeoDa 1.20.

Results

Population and farmers' markets descriptives

Out of the 3,232 cells containing a population, 808 (25%) were categorized as lower income, while 812 (25.12%) were identified as having a "high presence" of ethnic-racial minorities. Among the latter group, 425 cells (52.3%) were also classified as lower income, suggesting an expected association between race/skin color and income in Porto Alegre. These proportions mirror the figures discovered within the census tract grid (the original unit of

analysis in the 2010 Census): 25% in the former case and 25.12% in the latter, affirming the accuracy of the data interpolation to the hexagonal grid created by IPEA.

Figure 1 illustrates that out of the 44 total markets in the city (comprising 6 farmers' markets, 6 agroecological farmers' markets, and 32 of the model farmers' market type), 59% of them are situated in the central zone or along primary avenues, which have been encompassed within the group of "centralities" in Porto Alegre. Table 1 demonstrates that this percentage is the smallest among all categories of food establishments in the city. Additionally, the market concentration level (NNI=0.91) is also the lowest in comparison to other types of food outlets.

Figure 2 shows the spatial distribution of the markets overlaid on the distribution of binary cells indicating higher/lower income (2a) and race/skin color (2b). Among the 44 markets, 5 (11%) are positioned in cells with a high concentration of ethnic-racial minorities, and none are situated in lower-income cells. Consequently, there are no markets located in areas simultaneously characterized by a predominance of ethnic-racial minorities and lower income.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of street markets (diamond dots) in relation to the central area and main avenues (in dark gray) of Porto Alegre.

Source: Authors.

Accessibility

Table 2 displays accessibility for each mode of transportation, accompanied by the combined population residing in those specific cells. Upon closer examination of the extreme categories, it is evident that 21.1% of the population can reach a farmers' market on foot within 10 minutes, 26.7% by bus, and 58% by bicycle, while 88.8% can do so by car. Conversely, 26.5% of the city's total population resides in areas more than 30 minutes on foot from the nearest market, with 14.3% requiring more than 30 minutes by bicycle, 13.8% by bus, and only 0.4% by car.

Table 1. Number, location, and concentration of food establishments in Porto Alegre.

Type	N	% Center	% Avenues	% C+A	NNI
Farmers' markets	44	25	34	59	0.91
Supermarkets	289	25	44	69	0.55
Minimally processed	445	24	41	65	0.49
Mixed	3,637	48	29	77	0.29
Ultra-processed	6,840	28	28	64	0.36

Source: Authors.

Table 2. Minimum travel time in Porto Alegre to the nearest farmers' markets by type of transport (walking, bicycle, bus and car).

Time class	Cells (%)	Population (%)
Walking		
<10 min	320 (9.9)	293,216 (21.1)
10-20 min	624 (19.3)	447,531 (32.2)
20-30 min	464 (14.4)	280,121 (20.2)
>30 min	1,824 (56.4)	368,552 (26.5)
Total	3,232 (100)	1,389,420 (100)
Bicycle		
<10 min	1,018 (31.5)	805,735 (58)
10-20 min	644 (19.9)	349,516 (25.2)
20-30 min	153 (4.7)	36,132 (2.6)
>30 min	1,417 (43.8)	198,037 (14.3)
Total	3,232 (100)	1,389,420 (100)
Public Transport		
<10 min	421 (13)	370,587 (26.7)
10-20 min	958 (29.6)	628,754 (45.3)
20-30 min	447 (13.8)	198,601 (14.3)
>30 min	1,406 (43.5)	191,478 (13.8)
Total	3,232 (100)	1,389,420 (100)
Car		
<10 min	2,088 (64.6)	1,233,920 (88.8)
10-20 min	692 (21.4)	140,082 (10.1)
20-30 min	271 (8.4)	9,572 (0.7)
>30 min	181 (5.6)	5,846 (0.4)
Total	3,232 (100)	1,389,420 (100)

Source: Authors.

a) Darker cells = Lower income

b) Darker cells = High presence of racial minorities

Figure 2. Spatial distribution of street markets (diamond dots) in relation to hexagonal cells classified by income (left) and race/color (right).

Source: Authors.

Table 3 reveals that only 2.7% of the population residing in cells classified as lower income can reach the nearest market on foot in less than 10 minutes, 36.4% by bicycle, 3.9% by bus, and 69.3% by car. Conversely, 54.2% of the lower-income population needs more than 30 minutes to reach the nearest market on foot, with 32.3% by bicycle, 37.6% by bus, and only 1.2% by car. In contrast, only 21.6% of the higher-income population takes more than 30 minutes on foot, 11.2% by bicycle, 9.5% by bus, and a minimal 0.3% by car. Regarding race/skin color, 11.2% of the population in cells with a high minority presence can access a market in less than 10 minutes by walking, 46.2% by bicycle, 15.2% by bus, and 78.4% by car. In areas with a low minority presence, 26.2% can reach a farmers' market on foot within this time frame, 64% by bicycle, 32.5% by bus, and an overwhelming 94.1% by car.

On the other hand, 43.8% of the population in areas with a high minority presence needs to walk more than 30 minutes to the nearest market, with 23.9% by bicycle, 25.9% by bus, and just over zero by car. In other locations, 17.7% walk

more than 30 minutes, 9.3% by bicycle, 7.6% by bus, and 0.6% by car. All these differences are statistically significant in according to the chi-square tests for heterogeneity with $p \leq 0.001$.

Discussion

The farmers' markets in Porto Alegre exhibit a comparatively lower level of geographic concentration compared to other food stores, indicating a relatively balanced distribution across the city. This reflects the reality that their placement isn't solely guided by market principles as with typical businesses. Instead, their positioning is influenced by public supply policies aimed at bringing producers closer to consumers city-wide. However, approximately a quarter of the markets are concentrated in the central area of the city, indicating some level of concentration. In Porto Alegre, whose primary centrality ("*centro expandido*") is situated to the west of the geometric center, there appears to be an imbalance in the distribution.

Table 3. Minimum travel time in Porto Alegre to the nearest farmers' markets in association with income and race/skin color traits.

Time	Lower income*	Lower income*	Higher income*	Higher income*
	cells (%)	pop (%)	cells (%)	pop (%)
Walking				
<10 min	7 (0.9)	5,596 (2.7)	313 (12.9)	287,620 (24.4)
10-20 min	58 (7.2)	45,258 (21.5)	566 (23.3)	402,251 (34.1)
20-30 min	88 (10.9)	45,848 (21.7)	376 (15.5)	234,273 (19.9)
>30 min	655 (81.1)	114,270 (54.2)	1,169 (48.2)	254,282 (21.6)
Total	808 (100)	210,972 (100)	2,424 (100)	1,178,426 (100)
Bicycle				
<10 min	96 (11.9)	74,980 (36.4)	922 (38)	730,755 (62)
10-20 min	148 (18.3)	54,495 (26.5)	496 (20.5)	290,021 (24.6)
20-30 min	55 (6.8)	9,898 (4.8)	98 (4)	26,234 (2.2)
>30 min	509 (63)	66,621 (32.3)	908 (37.5)	131,416 (11.2)
Total	808 (100)	205,994 (100)	2,424 (100)	1,178,426 (100)
Public Transport				
<10 min	13 (1.6)	8,173 (3.9)	408 (16.8)	362,414 (30.8)
10-20 min	123 (15.2)	80,074 (38)	835 (34.4)	548,680 (46.6)
20-30 min	117 (14.2)	43,429 (20.6)	330 (13.6)	155,172 (13.2)
>30 min	555 (68.7)	79,318 (37.6)	851 (35.1)	112,160 (9.5)
Total	808 (100)	210,972 (100)	2,424 (100)	1,178,426 (100)
Car				
<10 min	350 (43.3)	146,303 (69.3)	1,738 (71.7)	1,087,617 (92.3)
10-20 min	258 (31.9)	58,132 (27.6)	434 (17.9)	81,950 (7)
20-30 min	104 (12.9)	4,040 (1.9)	167 (6.9)	5,532 (0.5)
>30 min	96 (11.9)	2,519 (1.2)	85 (3.5)	3,327 (0.3)
Total	808 (100)	210,972 (100)	2,424 (100)	1,178,426 (100)

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Table 3. Minimum travel time in Porto Alegre to the nearest farmers' markets in association with income and race/skin color traits.

Time	Higher minorities*	Higher minorities*	Lower minorities *	Lower minorities*
	cells (%)	pop (%)	cells (%)	pop (%)
Walking				
<10 min	45 (5.5)	52,556 (11.2)	275 (11.4)	240,660 (26.2)
10-20 min	115 (14.2)	108,697 (23.1)	509 (21)	338,834 (36.8)
20-30 min	129 (15.9)	102,562 (21.8)	335 (13.8)	177,559 (19.3)
>30 min	523 (64.4)	205,932 (43.8)	1,301 (53.8)	162,620 (17.7)
Total	812 (100)	469,747 (100)	2,420 (100)	919,673 (100)
Bicycle				
<10 min	229 (28.2)	217,027 (46.2)	789 (32.6)	588,708 (64)
10-20 min	194 (23.9)	122,069 (26)	450 (18.6)	227,447 (24.7)
20-30 min	60 (7.4)	18,559 (4)	93 (3.8)	17,573 (1.9)
>30 min	329 (40.5)	112,092 (23.9)	1,088 (45)	85,945 (9.3)
Total	812 (100)	469,747 (100)	2,420 (100)	919,673 (100)
Public Transport				
<10 min	64 (7.9)	71,445 (15.2)	357 (14.8)	299,142 (32.5)
10-20 min	221 (27.2)	190,330 (40.5)	737 (30.5)	438,424 (47.7)
20-30 min	148 (18.2)	86,411 (18.4)	299 (12.4)	112,190 (12.2)
>30 min	379 (46.7)	121,561 (25.9)	1,027 (42.4)	69,917 (7.6)
Total	812 (100)	469,747 (100)	2,420 (100)	919,673 (100)
Time	Higher minorities*	Higher minorities*	Lower minorities *	Lower minorities*
	cells (%)	pop (%)	cells (%)	pop (%)
Car				
<10 min	524 (64.5)	368,488 (78.4)	1,564 (64.6)	865,432 (94.1)
10-20 min	241 (29.7)	97,611 (20.8)	451 (18.6)	42,471 (4.6)
20-30 min	46 (5.7)	3,543 (0.8)	225 (9.3)	6,029 (0.7)
>30 min	1 (0.1)	105 (0.0)	180 (7.4)	5,741 (0.6)
Total	812 (100)	469,747 (100)	2,420 (100)	919,673 (100)

*Chi-square test with significance value <0.001 for all groups. Lower income: Hexagons classified with income < BRL 474.35 (1st quartile); Higher income: Hexagons classified with income >R\$ 474.35 (2nd, 3rd, 4th quartiles); Higher Minorities: Hexagons classified with the percentage of black, brown, indigenous and yellow ≥25%; Lower Minorities: Hexagons classified with the percentage of black, brown, indigenous and yellow <25%.

Source: Authors.

This observation aligns with prior research that highlights how areas outside the central zones of cities typically lack farmers' markets, potentially hindering a large portion of the population's access to these resources⁹⁻¹¹. Our accessibility analysis reinforces this, indicating that while markets are located in areas with significant residential presence, only about a quarter of the population can reach a market within a 10-minute walking or bus journey. In stark contrast, nearly 90% of the population can reach a market within the same timeframe using a car.

Our findings highlight advantages in terms of market accessibility for high-income areas, which is consistent with existing literature. Previous studies conducted in Brazil have indicated that regions with higher incomes tend to have a

greater presence of establishments selling fresh and minimally processed foods^{6,9-11}. Additionally, our results regarding locations with a predominantly white population align with Brazilian studies, such as the work by Honório *et al.*¹⁸, which examined racial disparities and concluded that areas with fewer options for healthy foods were more populated by Black, Brown, or Indigenous individuals. Similar studies in the United States have suggested that neighborhoods with a higher concentration of Black populations tend to have lower availability of healthy food options¹⁹.

The most economically disadvantaged segments of minority ethnic-racial groups can only achieve a level of accessibility to markets comparable to the white and high-income groups

by relying on a car for transportation. This underscores the historical advantages afforded to individual, motorized transportation in shaping Brazilian cities, both in terms of establishing activity locations and directing investments in the transportation system. This situation perpetuates disparities and underscores the privilege attached to motorized transportation, contributing to uneven access to essential resources and services, like access to food markets, among different socioeconomic and racial groups²⁰.

Despite these disparities, the bicycle has emerged as a viable alternative, facilitating short trips to markets for over half of the population. This underscores its effectiveness as an urban transportation mode¹⁹. However, in the Brazilian context, the use of bicycles remains highly limited, constituting only about 1% of trips in cities with over one million inhabitants in 2018²⁰. This low adoption is due not only to limited coverage and poor quality of cycling infrastructure in most cities but also to behavioral resistance from other road users. Additionally, cyclists encounter various forms of prejudice, further hindering the widespread acceptance and usage of bicycles as a primary means of transport in urban areas²¹⁻²³.

Due to the challenge of accessing farmers' markets within a short timeframe, individuals from socially disadvantaged backgrounds often resort to purchasing fresh food from the nearest and most accessible places, typically grocery stores and supermarkets. However, in these establishments, prices are generally higher, and the quality of products may be lower. This situation may lead to the purchase of smaller quantities of fresh foods and a prioritization of ultra-processed alternatives²⁴. This trend aligns with the prevailing reality in Brazil and many Global South countries, where the spatial organization of cities and the prevailing mobility systems tend to accentuate spatial inequalities, contributing to social inequities in food access, nutrition, and overall health^{25,26}.

Social inequities represent unjust variations between different groups within a population. These disparities encompass differences based on various factors including income, education, gender, access to opportunities, and socioeconomic status, among others. Additionally, racial inequities specifically pertain to differences between groups attributed to race or skin color, encompassing the essence of racism. This encapsulates unequal treatment, opportunities, or advantages and disadvantages experienced by distinct racial or ethnic groups within society²⁷. Moreover, the challenges faced by this popula-

tion in accessing FV can be seen as a manifestation of structural racism. Structural racism is defined as a type of racial discrimination perpetuated in society through customs, practices, and laws, becoming ingrained in people's daily lives²⁸. In this context, structural racism molds individuals' environments and opportunities, imposing additional barriers for black, brown, and indigenous communities in accessing healthy food options, potentially resulting in adverse health outcomes.

Strengths and limitations

The primary strength of this study lies in its pioneering nature, as it delves into the research on food environments in Brazil by bridging health sciences with urban sciences. It employs a more realistic methodology to evaluate intra-urban accessibility, comparing various population strata beyond traditional proximity analyses. Unlike most cited studies employing a "container" approach to assess accessibility, our study, to the best of our knowledge, is the first to consider real accessibility to street markets by different modes of transport using the physical road network of the city.

The results, however, should be interpreted while considering some limitations: (1) its ecological approach makes causal inference impossible at the individual level, but it can generate hypotheses and indicate paths for other study designs; (2) in this sense, it was necessary to work by measuring the accessibility of locations and, only then, computing the resident population, which leads to differences between the percentage of cells and population in each category in each mode that reflect the fact that the more central hexagons have more inhabitants than the peripheral ones; (3) the use of data from the 2010 Brazilian Census, already quite outdated, can mask changes in socio-spatial distributions.

In conclusion, our study highlighted the presence of social and ethnic-racial inequities in accessing farmers' markets in Porto Alegre. Moving forward, it's important to conduct similar studies employing comparable methodologies in other Brazilian capitals. This approach will help assess the consistency of these findings in different urban contexts, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the unequal dynamics and patterns of accessibility to farmers' markets across different regions in Brazil. Knowing these patterns allows for the improvement of healthy food supply policies with a focus on combating social inequities.

Collaborations

GL Rosa and FM Pasqual took part in the data analyses and interpretation of data. DC Borges took part in the analyses and interpretation of data and preparation of this manuscript. R Canuto and JCB Vargas are the coordinators of the project and overall outline; researching, analyzing and interpreting data; and in providing a critical review and final approval of the text to be published.

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